

EFFICACY OF ROSUVASTATIN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

Sadia Naz^{*1}, Tauqeer Ahmad², Aadil Shabbir³

^{*1,2}Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot

³Central Park Medical College

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Corresponding Author: *

Sadia Naz

Abstract

Background: Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a common chronic liver disorder closely associated with metabolic syndrome, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia. Pharmacological options for NAFLD remain limited, and statins have emerged as potential agents due to their lipid-lowering and pleiotropic effects. **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy and safety of rosuvastatin in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. **Methodology:** This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital, Sialkot, from September 2024 to January 2025. A total of 85 patients diagnosed with NAFLD were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. All patients received rosuvastatin 10 mg once daily for 12 weeks. Baseline and post-treatment assessments included liver enzymes, lipid profile, glycemic parameters, body mass index, and ultrasonographic grading of fatty liver. Patients were stratified into diabetic and non-diabetic groups for comparative analysis. **Results:** At baseline, diabetic patients had significantly higher liver enzyme levels than non-diabetics. After 12 weeks of therapy, significant reductions were observed in ALT, AST, ALP, and GGT in both groups ($p < 0.001$). LDL-C and triglyceride levels decreased significantly, while HDL-C increased. Ultrasonographic grading showed a significant shift toward lower grades of fatty liver, with a reduction in Grade 3 steatosis in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients. Rosuvastatin was well tolerated, with mild adverse events and no serious complications or treatment discontinuation. **Conclusion:** Rosuvastatin is an effective and safe treatment option for non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, leading to significant improvement in liver enzymes, lipid profile, and hepatic steatosis. Its benefits are evident irrespective of diabetic status, supporting its use in NAFLD patients with metabolic comorbidities.

INTRODUCTION

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is currently recognized as the most common chronic liver disease worldwide and has emerged as a leading indication for liver transplantation, with projections suggesting it may soon become the primary cause [1][2]. NAFLD is defined by excessive hepatic fat accumulation exceeding 5% of hepatocytes, occurring in the absence of significant alcohol intake

or other secondary causes of chronic liver disease. The disease spectrum ranges from simple hepatic steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which may further progress to advanced fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma [1][2]. Beyond its hepatic consequences, NAFLD is increasingly recognized as a systemic metabolic disorder. It is strongly associated with metabolic

syndrome, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance [3][4]. Due to its close relationship with insulin resistance and central obesity, NAFLD is now considered an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease, particularly atherosclerosis, which represents the leading cause of mortality in these patients rather than liver-related complications alone [3][4]. Recent epidemiological data indicate that NAFLD affects a substantial proportion of the global population. Meta-analyses and large systematic reviews estimate the worldwide prevalence of NAFLD to range between 25.2% and 29.8% [5]. In Pakistan, the burden appears even higher, with studies reporting a prevalence of 47% for NAFLD, while biopsy-proven NASH has been identified in 12.3% of affected individuals, underscoring the magnitude of this public health problem in the local population [6].

The pathogenesis of NAFLD is complex and multifactorial and remains incompletely understood. Current evidence suggests that insulin resistance plays a central role by increasing free fatty acid influx into the liver through enhanced peripheral lipolysis. Additional contributory mechanisms include increased hepatic lipid synthesis, impaired export of triglycerides via very-low-density lipoproteins, oxidative stress, mitochondrial and peroxisomal dysfunction, inflammatory cytokine and adipokine imbalance, and alterations in the intestinal microbiota [7]. These interacting pathways ultimately lead to hepatocyte injury, inflammation, and fibrogenesis, driving disease progression from simple steatosis to NASH. Despite the rising prevalence and clinical significance of NAFLD, effective pharmacological treatment options remain limited. Lifestyle modification remains the cornerstone of management; however, adherence is often suboptimal, and disease progression may occur despite non-pharmacologic measures. This has created a growing need for pharmacologic agents that target the underlying metabolic and inflammatory mechanisms of NAFLD and prevent its progression to advanced liver disease [7]. Statins have emerged as potential therapeutic agents in this context. As HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, statins effectively reduce cholesterol synthesis and improve dyslipidemia, a core feature of NAFLD. Given that hepatic accumulation of free cholesterol contributes

to lipotoxicity and hepatocellular injury, cholesterol-lowering therapy may play a beneficial role in disease modulation [8]. In addition to lipid-lowering effects, statins exhibit several lipid-independent pleiotropic properties, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-fibrotic, and endothelial-protective actions, which may be relevant in the pathophysiology of NAFLD and NASH [9][10].

Among statins, rosuvastatin has attracted particular interest due to its potent lipid-lowering efficacy and favorable pharmacokinetic profile. Experimental and clinical evidence suggests that rosuvastatin may improve hepatic steatosis and attenuate inflammatory and fibrotic processes within the liver. Its ability to modulate oxidative stress and improve mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation further supports its potential role in NAFLD management [9][10]. Although emerging studies suggest beneficial effects of rosuvastatin on liver enzymes, lipid parameters, and hepatic steatosis, evidence-based data remain limited, particularly in local populations. There is a need for well-designed clinical studies to evaluate the efficacy of rosuvastatin in improving biochemical, metabolic, and ultrasonographic features of NAFLD. Addressing this gap may help refine treatment strategies and support evidence-based clinical practice in the management of this increasingly prevalent disease.

Objective:

To evaluate the efficacy and safety of rosuvastatin in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

Methodology

This was a randomized controlled trial conducted at the Department of Medicine, Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital, Sialkot, September 2024 to January 2025. A total of 85 patients diagnosed with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease were enrolled using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. The sample size was calculated based on a reported prevalence of NAFLD of 12.3%, with a 95% confidence level and 7% margin of error. All enrolled patients received rosuvastatin 10 mg orally once daily at night for 12 weeks.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 25–65 years

- Diagnosed with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease as per operational definition
- Willingness to participate and provide informed consent
- Patients with controlled hypertension (systolic ≥ 130 mmHg and diastolic < 80 mmHg)
- Patients with controlled diabetes mellitus (HbA1c $< 6.5\%$), with or without medication

Exclusion Criteria

- Triglyceride levels ≥ 500 mg/dL or LDL-C levels ≥ 250 mg/dL
- Known history of coronary heart disease or atherosclerotic disease
- Familial hypercholesterolemia
- Uncontrolled hypertension or uncontrolled hypothyroidism
- Chronic kidney disease
- Known statin hypersensitivity
- Active hepatic dysfunction with liver enzymes or bilirubin ≥ 1.5 times the upper normal limit
- Unexplained elevation of serum creatine kinase > 3 times upper normal limit
- Use of non-recommended concomitant drugs or pregnancy
- Patients already taking statins or lipid-lowering drugs for a long duration

Data Collection

After obtaining ethical approval from the institutional review board, eligible patients were enrolled. Demographic and clinical data including age, gender, height, body weight, smoking habits, blood pressure, and comorbidities were recorded using a structured proforma.

Baseline abdominal ultrasonography was performed for all patients by a single experienced radiologist to minimize inter-observer variation, using a high-resolution B-mode ultrasonography system (Toshiba Xario 100) with a 5–7 MHz convex transducer. Fatty liver was graded as Grade 1, Grade 2, or Grade 3 based on hepatic echogenicity relative to the right kidney. Laboratory investigations including bilirubin,

alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, gamma-glutamyl transferase, serum creatinine, creatine kinase, fasting lipid profile, and HbA1c were performed at baseline and after 12 weeks of therapy. Patients were monitored for adverse events throughout the study period, and any spontaneous or elicited adverse effects were recorded. The primary endpoint was improvement in liver enzymes, lipid profile, body mass index, HbA1c, and ultrasonographic grading of fatty liver from baseline to 12 weeks.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic, biochemical, and radiological findings. The primary endpoint was normalization of liver enzymes, while secondary endpoints included improvement in lipid profile and ultrasonographic features of NAFLD. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The overall mean age of the study population was 47.6 ± 9.8 years. Diabetic patients were significantly older with a mean age of 50.2 ± 9.1 years compared to 46.1 ± 10.0 years in non-diabetic patients ($p = 0.04$). Male gender predominated in both groups (61.3% vs. 55.6% , $p = 0.61$). The mean BMI was higher in diabetic patients (29.0 ± 3.8 kg/m²) than non-diabetics (27.6 ± 3.4 kg/m²), though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$). Hypertension was significantly more prevalent among diabetics (67.7% vs. 31.5% , $p = 0.001$), while smoking status was comparable between groups (19.4% vs. 24.1% , $p = 0.61$).

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n = 85)

Variable	Total (n = 85)	Diabetic (n = 31)	Non-Diabetic (n = 54)	p-value
Age (years), mean ± SD	47.6 ± 9.8	50.2 ± 9.1	46.1 ± 10.0	0.04*
Male gender, n (%)	49 (57.6%)	19 (61.3%)	30 (55.6%)	0.61
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ± SD	28.1 ± 3.6	29.0 ± 3.8	27.6 ± 3.4	0.08
Hypertension, n (%)	38 (44.7%)	21 (67.7%)	17 (31.5%)	0.001*
Smokers, n (%)	19 (22.4%)	6 (19.4%)	13 (24.1%)	0.61

At baseline, diabetic patients had significantly higher liver enzyme levels, indicating more severe hepatic involvement. Mean ALT was 78.1 ± 19.4 IU/L in diabetics compared to 69.1 ± 17.5 IU/L in non-diabetics ($p = 0.02$). AST showed a similar pattern (66.7 ± 16.8 vs. 59.0 ± 15.3 IU/L, $p = 0.03$). GGT levels were also significantly higher in diabetics (92.6

± 30.8 IU/L) than non-diabetics (80.3 ± 27.4 IU/L, $p = 0.04$). ALP levels were numerically higher in diabetics (152.9 ± 34.1 IU/L) but this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.18$).

Table 2: Baseline Liver Enzyme Levels by Diabetes Status

Parameter (IU/L)	Total	Diabetic	Non-Diabetic	p-value
ALT, mean ± SD	72.4 ± 18.6	78.1 ± 19.4	69.1 ± 17.5	0.02*
AST, mean ± SD	61.8 ± 16.2	66.7 ± 16.8	59.0 ± 15.3	0.03*
ALP, mean ± SD	146.2 ± 32.4	152.9 ± 34.1	142.3 ± 31.2	0.18
GGT, mean ± SD	84.9 ± 29.1	92.6 ± 30.8	80.3 ± 27.4	0.04*

Both diabetic and non-diabetic patients demonstrated marked improvement in liver enzymes after 12 weeks of rosuvastatin therapy. In diabetics, ALT decreased from 78.1 ± 19.4 IU/L to 42.6 ± 12.8 IU/L, while in non-diabetics it declined from 69.1 ± 17.5 IU/L to 36.9 ± 10.4 IU/L ($p <$

0.001). AST levels fell from 66.7 ± 16.8 to 37.8 ± 11.4 IU/L in diabetics and from 59.0 ± 15.3 to 32.9 ± 9.1 IU/L in non-diabetics ($p < 0.001$). Similar significant reductions were observed in ALP and GGT across both groups, confirming consistent biochemical response irrespective of diabetic status.

Table 3: Changes in Liver Enzymes After 12 Weeks of Rosuvastatin

Parameter	Diabetic (Baseline → 12 wk)	Non-Diabetic (Baseline → 12 wk)	p-value
ALT (IU/L)	$78.1 \pm 19.4 \rightarrow 42.6 \pm 12.8$	$69.1 \pm 17.5 \rightarrow 36.9 \pm 10.4$	$<0.001^*$
AST (IU/L)	$66.7 \pm 16.8 \rightarrow 37.8 \pm 11.4$	$59.0 \pm 15.3 \rightarrow 32.9 \pm 9.1$	$<0.001^*$
ALP (IU/L)	$152.9 \pm 34.1 \rightarrow 122.6 \pm 28.4$	$142.3 \pm 31.2 \rightarrow 115.8 \pm 25.9$	$<0.001^*$
GGT (IU/L)	$92.6 \pm 30.8 \rightarrow 52.4 \pm 19.6$	$80.3 \pm 27.4 \rightarrow 47.5 \pm 17.9$	$<0.001^*$

Rosuvastatin produced significant lipid improvement in both groups. Diabetic patients showed a reduction in LDL-C from 154.9 ± 32.1 mg/dL to 98.6 ± 22.4 mg/dL, while non-diabetics improved from 151.2 ± 30.8 mg/dL to 92.4 ± 20.6 mg/dL ($p < 0.001$).

Triglycerides decreased from 211.6 ± 48.7 to 151.3 ± 36.9 mg/dL in diabetics and from 191.2 ± 44.2 to 137.5 ± 31.4 mg/dL in non-diabetics ($p < 0.001$). HDL-C increased significantly in both groups, from 37.9 ± 7.6 to 43.8 ± 8.0 mg/dL in

diabetics and 39.1 ± 8.1 to 45.6 ± 8.3 mg/dL in non-diabetics.

Table 4: Lipid Profile Changes by Diabetes Status

Parameter (mg/dL)	Diabetic	Non-Diabetic	p-value
LDL-C reduction	$154.9 \pm 32.1 \rightarrow 98.6 \pm 22.4$	$151.2 \pm 30.8 \rightarrow 92.4 \pm 20.6$	<0.001*
Triglycerides	$211.6 \pm 48.7 \rightarrow 151.3 \pm 36.9$	$191.2 \pm 44.2 \rightarrow 137.5 \pm 31.4$	<0.001*
HDL-C increase	$37.9 \pm 7.6 \rightarrow 43.8 \pm 8.0$	$39.1 \pm 8.1 \rightarrow 45.6 \pm 8.3$	<0.001*

A significant shift toward milder ultrasonographic grades of fatty liver was observed in both groups. Among diabetics, Grade 3 fatty liver decreased from 35.5% at baseline to 19.4% after treatment, while Grade 1 increased from 16.1% to 41.9%. In non-diabetics, Grade 3 declined

from 25.9% to 13.0%, and Grade 1 increased from 24.1% to 51.9%. These changes were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) and indicate meaningful structural improvement in hepatic steatosis following rosuvastatin therapy.

Table 5: Ultrasonographic Grading of NAFLD Before and After Treatment

Grade	Diabetic Baseline	Diabetic 12 wk	Non-Diabetic Baseline	Non-Diabetic 12 wk	p-value
Grade 1	5 (16.1%)	13 (41.9%)	13 (24.1%)	28 (51.9%)	<0.001*
Grade 2	15 (48.4%)	12 (38.7%)	27 (50.0%)	19 (35.2%)	0.02*
Grade 3	11 (35.5%)	6 (19.4%)	14 (25.9%)	7 (13.0%)	0.01*

Rosuvastatin was well tolerated in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients. Myalgia occurred in 9.7% of diabetics and 5.6% of non-diabetics ($p = 0.48$). Mild creatine kinase elevation was observed in 6.5% of diabetics and 3.7% of non-diabetics ($p = 0.57$). Gastrointestinal discomfort was infrequent and

comparable between groups (3.2% vs. 3.7%, $p = 0.90$). No patient developed serious adverse events or required treatment discontinuation, confirming the overall safety of rosuvastatin in this cohort.

Table 6: Safety and Tolerability of Rosuvastatin by Diabetes Status

Adverse Event	Total	Diabetic	Non-Diabetic	p-value
Myalgia, n (%)	6 (7.1%)	3 (9.7%)	3 (5.6%)	0.48
Mild CK elevation	4 (4.7%)	2 (6.5%)	2 (3.7%)	0.57
GI discomfort	3 (3.5%)	1 (3.2%)	2 (3.7%)	0.90
Serious adverse events	0	0	0	—
Treatment discontinuation	0	0	0	—

Discussion

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease is increasingly recognized as a major metabolic liver disorder with significant hepatic and extrahepatic consequences. In the present study, rosuvastatin therapy for 12 weeks resulted in significant biochemical, metabolic, and ultrasonographic improvement in patients with NAFLD, with consistent benefits observed in both diabetic and non-diabetic subgroups. These findings reinforce the emerging role of statins as a potentially beneficial therapeutic option in NAFLD beyond lipid lowering. At baseline, diabetic patients demonstrated more severe disease, reflected by significantly higher liver enzyme levels, including ALT (78.1 ± 19.4 IU/L vs. 69.1 ± 17.5 IU/L) and AST (66.7 ± 16.8 IU/L vs. 59.0 ± 15.3 IU/L). This observation is consistent with previous research, which has shown that insulin resistance and chronic hyperglycemia exacerbate hepatic steatosis and inflammatory activity, leading to greater biochemical derangement in diabetic individuals [11]. The higher prevalence of hypertension among diabetic patients (67.7% vs. 31.5%) further highlights the clustering of metabolic risk factors in this subgroup, as reported in previous research [12]. Following rosuvastatin therapy, a marked and statistically significant reduction in liver enzymes was observed in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients. ALT levels decreased to 42.6 ± 12.8 IU/L in diabetics and 36.9 ± 10.4 IU/L in non-diabetics, while AST declined to 37.8 ± 11.4 IU/L and 32.9 ± 9.1 IU/L, respectively ($p < 0.001$). Similar improvements in ALP and GGT were also noted. These findings align with previous research demonstrating that statins may reduce hepatic inflammation through lipid-lowering effects as well as pleiotropic mechanisms, including improved endothelial function and reduction of oxidative stress [13].

In addition to biochemical improvement, rosuvastatin produced substantial favorable changes in lipid profiles. LDL-C levels declined significantly in both diabetic (154.9 ± 32.1 to 98.6 ± 22.4 mg/dL) and non-diabetic patients (151.2 ± 30.8 to 92.4 ± 20.6 mg/dL), accompanied by reductions in triglycerides and increases in HDL-C. Previous research has consistently reported similar lipid-modifying effects of rosuvastatin, and these improvements are clinically relevant given that

cardiovascular disease remains the leading cause of mortality in patients with NAFLD [14]. Importantly, structural improvement in hepatic steatosis was also demonstrated on ultrasonography. The proportion of patients with Grade 3 fatty liver decreased markedly in both diabetic (35.5% to 19.4%) and non-diabetic (25.9% to 13.0%) groups, with a corresponding increase in Grade 1 fatty liver. These findings suggest that rosuvastatin may exert a beneficial effect on hepatic fat accumulation. Previous research has similarly shown regression of ultrasonographic steatosis grades following statin therapy, supporting a potential disease-modifying role [15]. The safety profile of rosuvastatin in this study was favorable. Mild adverse effects such as myalgia and transient creatine kinase elevation were infrequent and comparable between diabetic and non-diabetic patients, with no cases of serious adverse events or treatment discontinuation. This is in line with previous research, which has demonstrated that statins are generally safe in patients with stable chronic liver disease and do not increase the risk of hepatotoxicity when appropriately prescribed and monitored [16].

Conclusion

It is concluded that rosuvastatin therapy leads to significant biochemical, metabolic, and ultrasonographic improvement in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. In this study, 12 weeks of rosuvastatin resulted in a marked reduction in liver enzymes, improvement in lipid profile, and regression of fatty liver grades on ultrasonography. These beneficial effects were observed in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients, although baseline disease severity was greater among diabetics. Rosuvastatin was found to be safe and well tolerated, with only mild and transient adverse effects and no treatment discontinuation. Overall, rosuvastatin appears to be an effective therapeutic option in NAFLD, particularly in patients with associated metabolic risk factors, and may play a role beyond lipid lowering in improving hepatic steatosis and inflammation.

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